

CHARACTERISTICS OF DRAMA AS A CREATIVE METHOD

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Abstract: this article analysis the main features and characteristics of dramatization with its way of position that takes the events of a novel, short story, or even a long poem and create a theatrical production or film from them. The story may be altered to fit the new form.

Key words: dramatization, plays, dialogue, description, characters, methods, creation, performance, dramatic form, stories

A dramatization is the construction of a dramatic presentation of content describing events, whether they are genuine or imagined. Dramatization is possible in every media and can aid in children's educational and psychological growth. The creation of a dramatization raises potential legal concerns due to the depiction of real people and events as well as the usage of components from other people's fictitious works.

Dramatization refers to the performance of a narrative, real-life circumstance, event, feeling, or concept. Plays, puppet theater, radio theater, pantomime, pageants, processions, parades, clowning, dancing, skits, role plays, simulations, interviews, dialogue sermons, and monologues are just a few examples of the many different types of dramatization. A dramatization's main goal is to give its participants a fresh and engaging way to experience, comprehend, and communicate the subject matter. A dramatization is "the preparation of a television drama from a work which was not previously in dramatic form, for example, a prose narrative" in the context of television. Because dramatization is a technique that is especially well adapted to television, it is frequently used in ads that highlight the advantages of using an offered product. Although the terms "dramatization" and "adaptation" are

occasionally used synonymously, the BBC distinguishes between the two terms by stating that an adaptation is a preparation drawn from a dramatic work. When the events being dramatized are historical, this may also be considered a form of historical reenactment, and occurs within the genre of docudrama. In some cases, in conveying the lives of historical figures "dramatization is a necessity due to lack of documentation".

It has been said that dramatization is "a primitive instinct and that very early people expressed their thoughts and emotions through this medium, or at least through that of pantomime, which is so closely connected with it." In particular, "when children identify with the various characters in the story; it is natural for them to want to imitate those characters" Any attempt to describe an incident other than in a clinical sense necessitates some dramatization, to a certain extent:

Story exaggeration follows straight from effective storytelling. The re-telling of a narrative in its entirety or in part with a focus on spontaneity, cognition, action, identification, conversation, and sequence of events is known as story dramatization. The literature might then be appreciated more.

The drama's plot is intertwined with the characters that make up the story. Each character in a play has a distinct personality as well as a set of values and ideologies. The actors must bring the characters in the play to life. The protagonist is the central figure in the play with whom the viewer empathizes. He or she embodies the play's central topic. The antagonist or villain is the one who the protagonist clashes with. While some characters are active throughout the entire narrative, others are merely there to further the plot, while yet others are only seen briefly before or after key scenes and may or may not play a big part. In a play, dialogues are used to advance the plot.

The dialogue between the characters in the play serves as a means of telling the plot to the audience. The impression that the play has on the audiences is significantly influenced by the dialog's content and delivery. The dialogue between

characters is how the plot is made clear. They are crucial in illuminating the characters' characteristics. The words used, the accent, tone, speech pattern, and even the pauses in speaking convey much about the character and aid in illuminating not just his personality but also his social standing, history, and family background as provided by the play.

Children, through play, unconsciously begin to act out the dramatization of events in their lives and events of which they learn. Research has shown that "with a variety of students from different grades and socioeconomic backgrounds, through expression of feelings and thoughts in story dramatization and creative drama, self-concept is improved".

Legally, the creation of a dramatization may infringe on the intellectual property rights of the work from which it is derived. A dramatization of real events might infringe the personality rights of the individuals involved. However, it is also understood that the dramatization itself may be entitled to its own intellectual property protections:

The right to dramatize is an element of the author's copyright in any nation that recognizes author rights. However, the majority of nations believe that there is a limit beyond which a dramatization departs from the source material in such a way as to violate the novelist's right to dramatization. The author of a drama may draw inspiration from a central idea or theme in a book and create a piece that enshrines that notion while featuring a unique cast of people and events. The playwright will benefit from the copyright protection offered to a "original" play, whether the work is a faithful adaptation of the novel or is disjointed and devoid of subject.

References

1. Keith Selby, Robert Giddings, Chris Wensley, *Screening the Novel: The Theory And Practice Of Literary Dramatization* (2016), p. 24.
2. Kathleen J. Turner, *Mass Media and Popular Culture* (1984), p. 32.
3. Grace Evelyn Starks, "Dramatization", *Primary Education*, Volume 22, p. 529.

4. Nancy E. Briggs, Joseph Anthony Wagner, *Children's Literature Through Storytelling & Drama* (1979), p. 81.